

Entropy for a Particle in a Box, Special Relativity and Constraints

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Consider a particle with rest mass, m_0 , somewhere in a box (one dimensional) of length L . As a consequence, there is a uniform probability for the particle to be at any x point in the box and one might at first argue that Boltzmann entropy is proportional to $-k \ln(L)$. The problem with this seems to be that when viewed by a frame moving at constant $-v$, a Lorentz contraction would yield an entropy of $-k \ln(L \sqrt{1-vv/cc})$. A solution to this problem seems to be to incorporate a measurement mechanism, namely let L/L_1 be proportional to the number of places the particle may be in the box. L_1 is associated with a spatial resolution. Then, one has $-k \ln(L/L_1)$ in both frames. In this problem, there seems to be an entropy because of a lack of information about the position of the particle in L . If one were to measure the position of the particle at rest, there would be no probability and hence no entropy.

We argue, however, that there seems to be a deeper meaning to entropy than this which manifests itself in quantum mechanics. It seems that there are entropic consequences when one has possible states linked with constraints. In particular, consider a particle at rest at $x=0$ at t . The state of this particle is completely known, i.e. $E=m_0cc$, $p=0$, x,t . One might argue that x and t are completely decoupled, as are E and p because velocity is 0. If the particle moves, however, E' and p' are coupled as are x' and t' through the Lorentz transformation which uses the factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In other words, there are constraints imposed when a particle moves which are described by Lorentz invariants such as $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ and $A = -E't' + p'x'$. Thus, the decoupled x (from t) which may take on any value in principle in the rest frame does not hold if a particle moves. This, in turn, leads to spatial pockets, \hbar/p , in which one has uniform x probability, but due to the endpoints of these wavelength regions, one requires $\exp(ipx) = P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$, where P_1 is a complex probability. In other words, there is a spatial constraint at work in quantum mechanics for a moving object.

If one has a moving object in a box, one may no longer use the static $\ln(L/L_1)$ approach to counting state positions unless L_1 is equal to half a wavelength or greater, in which case, one does not really see the wavelength resolution. The constraint of a particle being in an infinite well of length L now is linked to $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ which follows from the $A = -Et + px$ constraint. Thus, there is a quantum spatial entropy due to $P(x) = CC \cos(pave x) \cos(pave x)$ in the box of length L , centered at $x=0$. Only $pave$ which allow for $\cos(pave x)$ to be 0 at the box edges are allowed. Thus, two spatial constraints come into play and must be reconciled with each other.

Again, if one uses L_1 as a measuring resolution, the spatial entropy does not change when viewed from a different frame. One may define a momentum entropy, but this also is frame independent.

Particle in a Box and Classical Entropy

If one considers a particle in a box of length L (one dimension) and there is a uniform spatial probability distribution, the Boltzmann entropy, $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$ should be proportional to:

S (Boltzmann) proportional to $-k \ln(L)$ ((1))

The problem with ((1)) is that when seen from a moving frame (constant $-v$), the box L is contracted to: $L \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ((2)), implying that the entropy is different when viewed in the moving frame.

A solution to this problem is to introduce a spatial measurement resolution L_1 so that the number of states in the rest frame is:

L/L_1 ((3))

Then, Boltzmann entropy becomes proportional to: $-k \ln(L/L_1)$ ((4))

This is invariant in the moving frame because L and L_1 contract in the same manner.

Thus, entropy depends on the measurement resolution.

We note that the entire notion of entropy follows from the idea of probability (i.e. a lack of information) in this problem. The length L is a constraint which limits the region in which this spatial lack of information exists. Thus, entropy (and probability) seem to be linked to allowed positions in space (time). This idea seems to have interesting consequences in special relativity.

Entropy Due to Special Relativity

Consider a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t . In such a case, one would argue that there is no probability or lack of information of any kind. In principle, however, one may generalize this problem by considering all allowable positions of the particle, whether the particle position has been measured or not. In such a case, the particle could, in principle, be at any x point with the same probability.

Given that there exists a Lorentz constraint (invariant) $A = -Et + px$, in the rest frame:

$E = m_0 c^2$, $t = \hbar / (m_0 c^2)$, $p = 0$ and $x \rightarrow \infty$ such that $px \rightarrow \hbar$ ((5))

Thus, $A=0$ and must also be 0 as seen in a moving frame. This means that in the moving frame (or for a moving particle), one no longer has the option of all x points. Now E', p', x', t' are constrained by the Lorentz transformation. For:

$A=0 = -E't' + p'x'$ one may have $t' = \hbar/E'$ and $x' = \hbar/p'$ ((6))

In other words, there are temporal and spatial resolutions which are linked with probability if a particle moves. One no longer has the infinite x range one had if a particle is at rest.

Matters become more complicated if one considers a probability $P_1(px)$ which respects the \hbar/p intervals, but satisfies:

$P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$ ((7))

This leads to $P_1 = \exp(ipx)$, a complex probability, which neither grows nor shrinks indefinitely.

As a result, there seem to be temporal and spatial probability considerations based on the idea of allowable positions in the rest frame together with the constraint $A = -Et + px$.

If one considers $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$, one may argue that a free particle has equal probability to be at any x and that the \hbar/p is “washed out” so to speak, but physically it is present for a 2-slit experiment and there is entropy in such a case because one does not know through which slit the particle passed.

Furthermore, if one considers an infinite potential well, one has two spatial constraints:

- (a) The usual classical L constraint linked with a usual spatial entropy
- (b) The \hbar/p constraint of a wavelength which is linked to the idea that a choice of all x in the rest frame (particle at rest) does not hold for a moving particle.

We argue that these two length constraints and their linked probabilities must be reconciled. This may be done using

$$P_1(px) + P_1(-px) = C \cos(px) \quad ((8))$$

Now, one no longer has a uniform x probability within L , but rather $((8))$, but the particle is still constrained to L , so $C \cos(px) = 0$ at $x = -L/2$ and $x = L/2$.

One may then calculate a spatial entropy using Shannon's equation:

$$S = -k \int dx C \cos(px) \ln\{C \cos(px)\} \quad ((9))$$

As shown in $((1))$ S proportional to $\ln(L)$. To have $((9))$ remain invariant when seen from a moving frame, one may add $-\ln(L_1)$ again, where L_1 is a measuring resolution sharper than \hbar/p .

One may decompose $\cos(px)$ into $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and calculate a momentum entropy: $-k \sum_p a(p) \ln(a(p))$. According to $((9))$, this entropy is proportional to $-\ln(L)$ as $n = \text{energy level} \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ and so there seems to be an issue of L is replaced with a contracted $L \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ unless one has a $+\ln(L_1 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})$ to remove the $1 - v^2/c^2$. This is like using $\ln(LL_1)$ instead of $\ln(L/L_1)$ in the spatial case. This is akin to p being linked with \hbar/L_1 .

The point we wish to make is that in the quantum case, the usual classical restricted length L must be associated with the quantum \hbar/p wavelength restrictions linked with $\exp(ipx)$. These affect the probability within L through $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In other words, the special relativistic constraint $A = -Et + px$ associated with possible positions of a particle in a rest frame or a moving particle (rest particle seen from a moving frame: constant $-v$) affect the spatial entropy of a particle in a box in quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one might at first argue that a particle at rest has $E = m_0 c^2$, $p=0$, x and t which are all known so there is no sense of probability or entropy. We suggest, however, that matters are more complicated. Even though a measurement has been done and it is known that the particle is at x and t , any x and t are allowed ($t>0$) in principle. Thus, in principle, the particle may be at any x with the same probability in the rest frame. Given that a Lorentz transformation changes E, p, x, t to E', p', x', t' , but that $A = \text{Lorentz invariant} = -E't' + p'x'$, one may see that for $p=0$, x may have any value such that px for $x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ approaches \hbar . For $t = \hbar/m_0 c^2$ one has $A = 0$. This means that if the particle is moving or viewed from a moving frame (constant $-v$), then one no longer has an infinite range for x , but rather \hbar/p as the range or wavelength.

This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability $P_1(px)$ such that $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$. As a result, there is an intrinsic probability for a moving particle due the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$. This leads to a probability density of $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for a particle restricted (localized) by a potential. In other words, this quantum density affects the spatial probability, but ultimately arises due to the fact that the infinite range of x for a particle at rest no longer holds for a moving particle.

We also note that for entropy to be the same in a rest and moving frame, one needs to introduce a measurement resolution L_1 . For example, instead of using $\ln(L)$ as proportional to entropy, one may use $\ln(L/L_1)$ where L_1 is the measurement resolution. In the quantum case, L_1 should be sharper than the wavelengths in the problem. Thus, entropy is linked with the measuring resolution, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box